

Politeness Strategy of Japanese Hotel Staff in Bali

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Abstract

This research is about Japanese politeness strategies. It aimed at determining the strategy of politeness in Japanese hotel staff in Bali when providing services to Japanese guests. The data was collected from conversations between Japanese guests and hotel staff were obtained by recording. The total number of participants were 32 participants, 15 person of hotel staff and 17 Japanese guests. The result of data analysis founded the hotel staff implemented the negative and positive politeness strategies. The negative politeness strategies can be seen from (1) formal utterance in the form of *keigo*, (2) utterance that does not contain *coercion* (giving choices). Positive politeness strategies can be seen from (1) utterance that contains attention, offers of assistance, sympathy for the needs of guests, (2) utterance that uses a variety of *futsugo* (daily language). This *futsugo* speech founded in conversations at the occupancy stage, especially in the speech handling guest complaints. While at the arrival, familiarisation and departure stages, there were no varieties of *futsugo*. This can be seen from all conversations where negative politeness strategies and positive politeness strategies applied in one dialogue, so that the appearance of *futsugo's* utterance was still considered acceptable or does not threaten guests' faces.

1. Introduction

Based on the theory of "guest cycle in the hotel" (Kasavana, 1993: 424), the hotel guest service process includes at least four stages, such as (1) pre-arrival, (2) arrival, (3) occupancy, (4) departure. In the pre-arrival stage, the activities carried out by hotel staff include: reservation, reconfirmation, pickup requests, and pre-arrival letters. At the arrival stage, services include: pick-up at the airport, welcome upon arrival at the hotel, check-in or registration process, giving room

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keys, explanation of facilities, such as breakfast hours, telephone numbers that can be contacted if there are problems and several important things other. After that the guest is escorted to the room by the bellboy, the luggage is carried by the bellboy, followed by an explanation about room facilities. The occupancy stage, namely services while guests stay at the hotel, such as ensuring room comfort, food and beverage service in restaurants, room service, and some services related to facilities provided to pamper guests, transportation when guests want to go out of the hotel and so on. At the departure stage, the services provided include check-out procedures such as bill settlement, key return, baggage handling, and delivery to the airport.

In this research, we will examine the strategy of politeness in Japanese hotel staff in Bali. We know that Japanese guests are potential guests for Bali tourism. Since the 1990s it has always been in the highest ranking or second in turns with guests from Australia. However, since 2009 the level of Japanese tourist visits to Bali has decreased by around 200 thousand. It is not too much increase, it tends to stagnate. The visits of foreign tourists in the last five years have been dominated by tourists from China. Australian tourists remain at the top. Japan is in the seventh place behind France, America and England. When viewed from the average tourist expenditure, Australian tourists spend an average of IDR 13.4 million for person, Japan an average of IDR 11.19 million p person, and China IDR 9.66 million for person. Although in terms of the number of tourists from China, in terms of expenditure, Japanese tourists are more than Chinese tourists (Bisnis.com.Denpasar. 22 October 2018).

The average length of stay for Japanese tourists is 5 days 4 nights. Most (74%) choose to stay in 5-star hotels or luxury hotels, such as in Nusa Dua, Jimbaran, Kuta and Ubud with rates ranging from \$ 600 to \$ 1,500 overnight. Seeing this potential, it is necessary to make efforts to increase the visit of Japanese tourists to Bali as it was during its heyday in the 1990s. One of them is by improving services in hotels.

The service at the hotel is a little different from other services. In the hospitality industry, services are regulated according to hotel procedures. For example, reception service procedures, reception staff will perform their duties according to hotel rules, such as:

- 1) Say hello, say welcome and offer to help
 - 2) Ask if the guest has booked a room
 - 3) If the guest has already booked a room, check again at the system
 - 4) Guests fill out the registration form
 - 5) Reception gives room key and guest card
 - 6) Say enjoy your stay at this hotel
 - 7) Give instructions to belboys to escort guests to the room as well as carry guests' luggage.
- (Bagyono, 2012: 109).

The hospitality industry makes these rules with the aim of preserving the quality of service staff to guests. The physical beauty of the hotel would be meaningless if the service disappoints guests. Guests are very important people. Guests are parties who buy hotel products. As the buyer of the product, guests are entitled to a pleasant and satisfying service. Guest satisfaction is a main priority in the management of a hotel business. If the guest is satisfied, then he will come back, give a positive review of the hotel, and of course this will also increase the hotel's reputation in the public's eye which will have an effect on attracting potential guests.

Hospitality services cannot be separated from verbal interaction. Verbal interactions are manifested by polite and friendly speech, formal language and formal attitudes as expressions of respect for guests. The service at the hotel also includes verbal elements. Communication skills are important in serving guests. According to Blue & Harun (2003: 77) language service (verbal hospitality) is a skill that must be mastered by tourism actors, such as: (1) how to greet guests, 2) how to ask for and provide the necessary information, 3) how to respond to questions / requests guests, 4) how to use body movements, 6) how to deal with guest complaints.

The relationship between guests and tourism actors is an asymmetrical relationship, so that the host always implements formality in services, including procedures for communicating with guests. For example, when guests arrive, greet with the words "welcome to hotel X". Greet guests as "okyaku sama". The language used is a variety of keigo (respectful language) as an expression of staff respect towards guests. If it is related to Brown & Levinson's (1987) politeness theory, then service speech in hospitality is more likely to use negative politeness strategies. This is in line with the opinion of Usami (2001) that negative politeness strategies are always used by Japanese society when serving others. Negative politeness strategies are manifested in keigo speech, to show formality, respect for the other person (hearers / addressee).

The study of language in the domain of hospitality is a pragmatic study, which is to look at the spoken language used in the context of a hotel service situation. Usually tourism actors will try to act politely and follow politeness strategies when serving guests or tourists. By considering the role of the host, communicative interaction is built to avoid actions that can disturb the feelings of guests. To minimize facial threats to speech partners, Brown & Levinson (1987) describe a model of politeness strategy by considering faces or self-images. According to Brown & Levinson, faces consist of two kinds, positive faces and negative faces. A positive face shows solidarity, closeness, a desire to be part of a speech partner, a desire to be close. A negative face shows a desire not to be disturbed, to keep your distance. Tourists have different characters in communicating. European tourists are more open, close like friends. Meanwhile, Japanese tourists keep their distance. This is the face of each nation. Therefore, as tourism actors, hotel staff must know how to treat guests according to their character. By looking at the context of the speech situation in hospitality services, this study will analyze the speech of hotel staff when providing services to Japanese guests. How do they bring their Japanese politeness strategy to Japanese guests? For that we need a theory of politeness strategies by Brown & Levinson's and to support it we used the variety of Japanese.

Politeness according to Brown & Levinson (1987) is an attitude of concern for the face, both the speaker's and the hearer's. Face in this case does not mean physical appearance, but rather refers to image or self-esteem. Face is a reflection of language that is first seen in a communication event. Therefore, the face is very important, the face must be cared for, respected, and guarded. So the essence of politeness is the ability to always maintain self-respect, feelings, and honor, both oneself and others. Brown & Levinson distinguish two types of "face", namely positive face, which means showing solidarity, closeness, a desire to be part of the other person. Meanwhile, negative face shows the desire not to be disturbed.

In Brown and Levinson's (1987: 74) politeness model, there are three scales to determine the high and low levels of speech politeness. The three scales were determined contextually, socially and culturally, including (1) Distance, the social distance between the Speaker and Listener, the level of intimacy (2) Power, the extent to which the Speaker can impose on the speech partner and (3) Rank of Imposition, how much the speaker's speech will give burden to the listener.

Brown & Levinson (1987: 60) identified four politeness strategies to guard against threats. The four strategies are (1) bald-on record strategy (without strategy), (2) positive politeness strategy (familiarity strategy), (3) negative politeness strategy (formal politeness strategy), (4) off-record politeness strategy (indirect or disguised strategy).

The positive politeness strategies include: 1) paying attention to what the interlocutor is needed, 2) using markers of group solidarity, fostering an optimistic attitude, 3) involving speech partners in the activities of speakers, 4) offering / promising something, 5) giving praise to speech partners, 6) avoiding mismatch, and 7) being funny. Meanwhile, negative politeness strategies include: 1) expressing indirectly, 2) using hedges or question sentences, 3) being pessimistic, 4) not burdening, 5) using the passive form, 6) apologizing, and 7) using the plural form.

Japanese has four levels of language formality. The languages classified as sonkeigo (honorific language), kenjyōgo (humility language), teineigo (usual formal language) and futsūgo (daily

language). Sonkeigo, kenjyougo teineigo are the group of keigo. Keigo is a kind of respectful language that is intended to respect the interlocutor and the person being spoken to. In choosing the form of keigo, several factors need to be considered, such as: the relationship between the speakers, who the other person is talking to, how close they are, the situation and the conditions. Kaneko (2014: 162) mentions that Japanese people speak politely when they meet someone for the first time, usually using teineigo as a neutral, respectful language. Then they will choose their language after getting to know each other. Kaneko explained that there are five things that determine the choice of keigo language, namely, (1) age, (2) social position, (3) service background, (4) uchi-soto concept and (5) closeness. Japanese never use keigo when talking with their own family, even though to the elder, such as parent, grand mother, grand father. They use futsugo.

Songkeigo is referring to actions of the listener raising his position. Direct expression of respect are characterized by (1) the use of prefixes *o* or *go* in front of noun, such as *okyaku sama* (guest), *onimotsu* (luggage), *gotouchaku*(arriving). (2) pattern *~ni narimasu* (verba structure), (3) passive form (*~reru* or *~rareru*), (4) special verbs such as *irrasharu* (to go, to come), *meshiagaru* (to eat or to drink) and so on. (5) attaching suffix *~san* or *~sama* after other people's name.

Kenjyougo is talking about your own actions, humbling yourself, indirect expression of respect. Is characterized by (1) the pattern "*o* or *go* + *shimasu* (verb structure), (2) using special verbs such as *haiken suru* (to see), *itadaku* (to eat, drink, to receive). (3) prefixes *o* or *go* + Noun that indicate actions as such *ohanashi* (speech/story), *odenwa* (phone call), *gokakunin*(confirmation).

Teineigo is polite language, is characterized by (1) the use of the verb ending *~masu*, (2) nouns and adjectives end with copula *~desu*. The use of teineigo has nothing to do with increasing or decreasing speech. Futsugo is a form of informal language used when speech is addressed to people who are close, such as family members, there is no social distance, and their age and position are below the speakers. Futsugo is translated as ordinary language, meaning that the language does not have an element of respect. Futsugo has a basic form of verb markers or in Japanese it is called *gokan*. Every nouns and adjective words will end with the copula "*da*" which has a function as a predicate.

There are several sentence patterns including futsugo, for example in the form of a question sentence, but not followed by an interrogative word, spoken in an ascending tone, as an expression of a question word. For example: *kore ikura?* How much is this. *Ima Nanji?* What time is it now? If you change to teineigo, just add the copula *desu ka?*

2. Materials and Methods

This study was conducted to observe the interaction between Japanese guest and hotel staff in Bali. The data is obtained by recording the dialogue between hotel staff and guests while performing services. The recording process is carried out by hotel staff secretly with cellphone recording aids. The data was conducted from May till August in 2019 in which these months are a lot of Japanese tourist visits to Bali. There were 17 recorded data from the arrival at the airport, arriving at the hotel, stay at the hotel, till departure.

The sampling used a random sampling technique. From the number of 73 five star hotel in Bali, it takes 10 hotels for sample in this research. They are Padma Resort-Legian, Intercontinental Resort-Jimbaran, the Four Seasons- Jimbaran, Ayana-Jimbaran, Grand Ina Kuta Bali, Melia Bali- Nusa Dua, Ritz Carlton-Nusa Dua, Conrad Bali-Nusa Dua, Grand Hyatt-Nusa Dua, Alila Ubud. The hotel staff used as subjects are staff of airport representative, bellboy, doorman, guest relation officer, receptionist, cashier and waiter or waitress. The total number of the participants are 32 participants, which consists of 15 person of hotel staff and 17 Japanese guests.

3. Results and Discussions

Research related to the language of hospitality has been conducted by Kristianto (2017), Blue & Harun (2003). Kristianto conducted the research in Bali, with European tourist objects. Kristianto's research results illustrate that hospitality language consists of two types, such as negative hospitality and positive hospitality. Negative hospitality is shown by respectful language, maintaining distance, giving freedom hospitality to guests, not disturbing the guests' territory. Formality in language style, applying standard language for tourism services, such as services in hotels, travel agents, airports, restaurants and other formal places. Meanwhile, the language of positive hospitality tends to be casual / daily language. It can be seen in the dialogue between tourists and surf coaches, beach boys, service sellers in informal places, such as on beaches, markets. By adopting the guest cycle theory from Kasavana (1993), Blue & Harun (1998) identified service language at four stages, (1) arrival, (2) recognition, (3) involvement, and (4) departure, as shown in this table below

The commercial arrivall–departure hospitality cycle

Stage	Activity	Language used
Arrival	Pick-up service in some hotels; luggage may be carried by porters; registration at the reception. All services are commercial	Greeting by driver, welcome by receptionist. Routine and rehearsed language used. Formal question - answer transactions in formal tone. Varies with category of hotel
Familiarisation	Receptionist briefs guest on what and where in-house facilities are available, and on meal and check-out times; guest may also read in-house brochures and ask questions about hotel	Briefing style, rehearsed messages, additional questions and answers, formal tone, language use varies according to category of hotel
Engagement	Independent use of facilities in rooms and in different sections of the hotel. Popular items include: TV, restaurant and bar, pool, gymnasium, sauna, disco	Mostly formal and impersonal, but may depend on how long guest stays in a hotel. Difficult to predict exact language needs other than those relating to use of facilities
Departure	Luggage transfer, preparation of bill, perfunctory farewell conversation	Mostly rehearsed language, mostly formal and impersonal

To analyze the politeness of the speech of hotel staff and Japanese guests, it will be studied with Brown & Levinson's (1987) politeness theory by looking at the dialogue from arrival to departure stages as in the above table.

The use of language at the arrival stage

Welcome greeting to guests by drivers, reception staff. The using of language that has been used and trained. Questions and answers between guests and staff in formal language, formal intonation. The following is the conversation data of hotel staff and Japanese guests during pick-up process in airport.

Data 1.

Topic : guests pick-up in Airport

The Interactants:

AR : 53 yrs / M (Four Seasons hotel)

G : a husband and wife, 45 years old

The first meeting

The context of the speech situation: Wawan, an Airport Representative (AR) staff pick up a guest named Mr. Tanaka at Ngurah Rai airport. AR while carrying the hotel sign board reading "Four Seasons Hotel", waiting for guests at the arrival door on the right. While observing every passenger who left the arrival door, a couple of Japanese tourists approached Wawan.

AR : バリへいらっしゃいませ すみませ。田中様でしょうか

Bali e irasshaimase. Sumimasen, Tanaka -sama deshou ka? (a)

Welcome to Bali. Sorry , are you Mr.Tanaka?

Guest : はい

Hai.

AR : フォーシーズンホテルのお客様でしょうか

Four Seasons hoteru no okyakusama deshou ka (b)

Are you hotel Four seasons' guests?

Guest : はい、そうです

Hai, soo desu.

Yes, I am

AR : バリへいらっしゃいませ。はじめまして、フォーシーズンホテルフォーシーズンホテルのワワンと申します。どうぞよろしくお願ひします。

Bali e irasshaimase. Hajimemashite, Four seasons hoteru no (c)

Wawan to mooshimasu. Doozo yoroshiku onegashimasu.

Welcome to Bali. I am Wawan from Four Seasons hotel. Nice to meet you.

Guest : よろしくお願ひします

Yoroshiku onegai shimasu

You are welcome, nice to meet you too

AR : お荷物はそろっていますか。お持ちしましょうか。どうぞこちらへ

Onimotsu wa soroteimasu ka. Omochi shimashou ka. Doozo kochira e

Is your luggage complete? Let me bring it

Please go to this way (go to the vehicle)

Guest : はい

hai

Yeah.

The data above is a dialogue between representative airport (AR) staff and Japanese guests. The participants had never met before, so the loading rate was very high. The context of the speech situation is pick-up at the airport. AR staff is waiting for guests at the points that have been explained to guests at the time of reservation via email. AR staff brings the hotel sign board, so guests can recognize him. When the guest approached, the AR staff said "Bali e irasshaimase" (welcome to Bali). AR staff said "Bali e irasshaimase" as an effort to show warm acceptance of guests, the desire to reduce distance from guests. This is a form of positive politeness strategy.

As a guest pick-up procedure, hotel staff must re-confirm the identity of their guests. To protect the face of the guest, when asking the name of the guest, it starts with the words "Sumimasen" sorry for the utterance "sumimasen, Tanaka - sama deshou ka" (sorry, are you Mr. Tanaka?) kopula "deshou ka?" also a marker of keigo (respectfull language) In the next utterance the, AR staff also used the copula "deshouka?" as in the speech "Four Seasons hoteru no okyakusama deshou ka" (Are you a guest of the Four Seasons hotel).

The strategy used by AR staff to ascertain the identity of this guest is the negative politeness strategy sub-strategy 6, which is to start the speech with the word "sorry" to the addressee (hearers). It is done by AR staff in order to protect the addressees' face (hearers). After making sure

that the guest being picked up was a guest of the Four Seasons hotel named Tanaka, the AR staff introduced himself and invited the guest to the car, while offering to bring the guests luggage, with the words "onimotsu omochi shimashou ka" (let me bring your luggage). The offering form is seen at the end of the verb with the addition of the suffix "~ mashou ka" (let's..). The form of offering includes positive politeness strategies, Sub strategy 12 (speakers involve speech partners in activities), it can be seen from the verb mashou ka, as a form of offer. This speech also implements the positive politeness strategy of sub strategy 1, paying attention to addressee (hearers) by offering help. So it can be said that in the utterance "Onimotsu omochi shimashou ka" more than one politeness strategy has been used, negative politeness strategies and politeness strategies. From the sentence structure, a variety of keigo is used. This is one of the characteristics of negative politeness strategies. When viewed from the point of view of the meaning of speech, it is a positive politeness strategy, such as giving attention by offering help to the addressee (hearers).

From the data 1 dialogue, it can be said that AR staff have performed speech acts that have implemented positive politeness strategies and negative politeness strategies. Positive politeness strategies are characterized by the efforts of AR staff to pay attention, offering assistance to guests. Negative politeness strategies can be seen from the use of a variety of respect in every speech. This can be seen from 1) the addition of the prefix o before nouns, 2) the sentence pattern "o + verb renyoukei + shimasu, 3) kopula deshou ka, 4) the use of special keigo verbs such as irassaimasu and mooshimasu.

Data 2.

Topic : Welcoming guests arriving at the hotel

The Interactants:

Doorman : 20 years (M) Padma hotel

Guest : 27 years (M), 25 (F)

The first meeting

Situation context: The doorman staff stands ready to wait for guests to arrive. When guests arrive at the hotel get out of the vehicle, the doorman opens the vehicle door, while saying welcome to the guests. Beside the doorman stood, it stands the ambassador staff who were tasked with pinning flowers in the ears of guests as an expression of welcome.

Doorman : パトマホテルへいらっしゃいませ。

Padma hoteru e irasshaimase.

Welcome to Padma hotel

(The doorman while opening the vehicle door and Ambassador staff ready to pin the flowers on the ears of guests)

Doorman : お荷物は全部でございますか。

Onimotsu wa zenbu de gozaimasu ka?

Are all these luggages are yours?

Guest : はい、そうです。

Hai, soo desu.

Yeah, alright

Doorman : お荷物を持ちます。フロントへどうぞ。ベルボーイがフロントへご案内します

Onimotsu o omochi shimasu. Furonto e doozo. Bellboy ga furonto e goannai shimasu.

Oke, let me bring your luggage. Bellboy will escort you to the front office.

Guest : ありがとう

Arigatoo

Thank you

The dialogue above occurs in the context of the situation when guests have just arrived at the hotel. When getting out of the vehicle guests are greeted by the doorman and ambassador staff. The doorman opened the vehicle door, greeted with the words "Padma hoteru e irasshaimase" (Welcome to the Padma hotel). The ambassador staff is tasked with pinning flowers or garlands (garlands) to guests. The friendly attitude of the hotel staff is a manifestation of the positive politeness strategy, namely paying attention to guests and efforts to reduce distance from guests. Irassaimase (welcome) also means that the staff is ready to help guests' needs. In the content section of the conversation, negative politeness strategies are used, such as the utterance "Onimotsu wa zenbu de gozaimasu ka?" (Do you have everything in your luggage?) Add prefix "o" to "nimotsu". The copula "~ de gozaimasu" is a form of teineigo.

At the end of the conversation, positive politeness strategies are used, such as the speech "Onimotsu o omochi shimasu" (we bring your stuff). "Furonto e doozo" (please go to the front office). "Bellboy ga furonto e goannai shimasu" (bellboy will escort you to the front office). These utterances show an element of concern for speech partners. This indicates that the doorman staff has implemented a positive politeness strategy. Based on the sentence structure, the speech is a form of keigo (respectful language). Look at the verb "o mochi shimasu" and "go annai shimasu". These two patterns are markers of kenjyogo (humble language) politeness.

From data 2, it is shown that doorman staff uses a variety of songkeigo and kenjyogo. This variety is used by the doorman as an expression of respect to guests. When viewed from the sentence structure, all the utterance in Data 2 uses a variety of keigo, it can be said that the doorman has implemented a negative politeness strategy. It can be seen from the use of keigo (respectful language). On the other hand, positive politeness strategies are also applied, when welcoming guests, namely expressing a friendly, warm and attentive welcome at the beginning of the conversation. At the end of the conversation, a positive politeness strategy was also shown, seen in the utterance that reflected concern for guests by bringing guest items and escorting guests to the front desk. So it can be said that in a dialogue a positive politeness strategy is used at the beginning of the discussion. In negative politeness strategy in the content of the conversation, re-used positive politeness strategies at the end of the conversation. In the content section of the conversation, negative politeness strategies are applied, such as formal speeches containing the procedures for the service of the doorman to guests arriving at the hotel.

From the dialogue above, it is also known that in one utterance, two politeness strategies are also applied at once, as seen at the beginning of the conversation and the end of the conversation. Positive politeness strategies when viewed from the meaning of speech and negative politeness strategies when viewed from the sentence structure that uses a variety of keigo

The using of Japanese at Familiarisation Stage

This stage is the stage of introduction to guests. Like when checking in, asked for the name of the guest, identity like a passport. Guests who stay at the hotel for the first time are greeted with the words "X hoteru e irasshaimase". Meanwhile, the repeater guests were greeted with a welcome home greeting, X-sama. At this stage for guests, it is an introduction to the atmosphere of the hotel, including an introduction to hotel staff. Physically, it introduced hotel facilities. For example, where is the restaurant, the location of the swimming pool, the direction to the beach, the emergency exit, an explanation of the facilities in the hotel room and so on.

Data. 3.

Topic : check in hotel
The Interactants:

Front office : 24 / M Padma hotel

Guest : 2 people (25 / F)

The first meeting

The context of the speech situation: after arriving at the hotel, the bellboy is escorted to the front desk to do the check in process.

Front office : パトマホテルにいらっしゃいませ

Padma hoteru ni irasshaimase

Welcome to Padma hotel

Guest : チェックインしたいんですが

chekkuin shitain desu ga....

I want to check in

Front office : かしこまりました。お名前をお願いします

kashikomarimashita. Onamae o onegaishimasu.

Alright. What is your name?

Guest : こじり恵みです。

Kojiri Megumi desu.

Front office : ご予約のお客様ですか

goyoyaku no okyakusama desu ka?

Are you a reserved guest?

Guest : はい、今日から三泊です

hai, kyoo kara sanpaku desu.

Yes, from today I three nights

Front office : 少々お待ちください

shooshoo omachi kudasai.

Please wait a moment.

(staf check guests resevetion in system)

大変お待たせしました。湖尻恵みさまですね。

Taihen omatase shimashita. Kojiri Megumi sama desu ne.

I am so sorry for waiting. Mrs. Kojiri Megumi ?

Guest : はい、そうです

hai, soo desu.

Yes, right

Front office : 今日から三泊シングル部屋ですね

kyoo kara sampaku, singuru, hitoheya desu ne.

From today is three nights, single, one bedroom, alright?

Guest : ええ

ee

Yes.

Front office : 宿泊カードをお書きします。パスポートをお願いします

shukuhaku kaaado o okaki shimasu. Paasupooto o onegaishimasu.

I fill your stay card, you passport, please

Guest : はい、これです

hai, kore desu

It is

Front office : ありがとうございます。こちらにシャインをお願いします。

Arigatoo gozaimasu. Kochira ni shain o onegaishimasu.

Thankyu. Your signature, please

- Guest : はい。
hai
Ok
- Front office : ご出発日は十五日ですね
goshuppatsu bi wa 15 nichi desu ne.
Your departure on 15 right?
- Guest : はい
Hai
Yes.
- Front office : お支払いはどのようになさいますか
oshiharai wa donoyooni nasaimasu ka?
How about the payment?
- Guest : クレジットカードでお願いします
kurejitto kaado de onegaishimasu.
By credit card
- Front office : はい、かしこまりました。
hai, kashikomarimashita.
Alright
どうもありがとうございました
Doomo arigatoo gozaimashita.
Thank you
(While give back the credit card to the guest)
こじりめぐみ様のお部屋は1412ごしつ、4階です
Kojiri Megumi sama no oheya wa 1412 goshitsu, 4 kai desu
Mrs. Kojiri Megumi, room number 1412, floor 4
少々お待ちください。ベルボーイがお部屋までご案内します。
Shooshoo omachi kudasai. Berubooi ga oheya made goannai shimasu.
Please wait a moment. Bellboy will take you to your room.
- Front office : どうぞごゆっくり
doozo goyukkuri
Good night.
(When bellboy comes and he take the guest to her room)

Data 3 is a conversation between guests (25 yrs / F) and FO staff (24 yrs / M) in a formal situation. The meeting is on the first day, and it's the first time guests stay at the hotel. At the beginning of the conversation, the staff of the FO showed a friendly welcome to guests, with greetings of "welcome", with the words "Padma hoteru e irasshaimase". This speech shows that the FO staff has implemented a positive politeness strategy, namely being friendly, showing attention to guests in the hope that guests will respond well, and attracting sympathy for guests to reduce the distance between guests and staff.

In this content section, according to the check-in process handling procedure, FO staff must confirm the identity of the guest, such as name, passport, proof of hotel reservation (if the guest has made a previous reservation), length of stay, room type and method of payment. "Onamae o onegaishimasu" (please your name). In this data, there are many songkeigo nouns, such as oheya (room), oshiharai (method of payment), goyoyaku (reservation), goshuppatsubi (day of departure). The addition of the prefix o and go to the noun is a characteristic of the songkeigo variety (honorific style).

The phrase "onegaishimasu" means ask or beg, comes from the verb "negau", then goes through a conjugation process to the pattern "o + verb negai + shimasu (kenjyougo style). The speech is direct speech. To reduce the face threat to guests, the verb "onegaishimasu" was chosen. The verb onegaishimasu is often used for subtle request sentences, so hotel staff is often use this verb when asking for something from guests or asking guests to do something. Other examples are "pasupooto o onegashimasu" (ask for your passport), "shain o onegaishimasu" (please sign your name). The politeness strategy used by the FO staff in this speech is the negative politeness strategy. This is marked by the use of the kenjyougo and songkeigo salutes.

In data 3 also found several expressions of respect used by FO staff when helping guests during the check-in process, such as; "Hi, kashikomarimashita" (yes, I understand) this phrase is more subtle than "Hi, wakarimashita" (yes, I understand). "Shooshoo omachi kudasai" (please wait a moment) this phrase is more subtle than "chotto matte kudasai". The phrase "Doozo goyukkuri" (have a good rest) is more subtle than "oyasuminasai". These phrases are expressions of staff respect towards guests and are commonly used in hospitality service communications.

In utterance "oshiharai wa donoyooni nasaimasu ka?" (How about the payment?) This speech has high flexibility, does not seem pushy, it gives free space to guests so that guests have many choices in how to pay. From this speech, it can be seen that the FO staff has applied a negative decree, namely a speech that is not coercive but gives a choice to the speech partner. (Addressee / hearer). At the end of the conversation, the FO staff showed again a positive politeness strategy, which was an element of concern and empathy for guests. Seen in the utterance "Shooshoo omachi kudasai. ga oheya made goannai shimasu" ("Please wait a minute. The bellboy will escort you to the room). After the bellboy arrived, the FO staff continued to express their concern by saying doozo goyukkuri (have a good rest).

The actions of the FO staff also contain the aim of being impressed by the hospitality and services provided. The hospitality industry, image, image are things that must be properly maintained. For the sake of getting guest visits. Based on the analysis, it can be said that at the beginning of the conversation the FO staff had applied a positive politeness strategy. In the content section, negative politeness is applied, in utterances regarding the check-in process service, such as when confirming guest names, passport numbers, signatures, payment methods. The negative politeness strategy in the content of the conversation can be seen from 1) the use of the phrase form of respect, 2) the verb respect, 3) the prefix o and go in nouns. At the end of the conversation, the staff used a positive politeness strategy, such as by paying attention to guests in sub-strategy 1 (Speaker give attention to Heares) and sub-strategy 5 (Speaker seeking Heares approval on a topic). Having viewed data 4, it can be seen that at the beginning of the conversation the FO staff used a positive politeness strategy. in the content section, a negative politeness strategy is used, at the end of the conversation a positive politeness strategy is used again. The following data is also a conversation at the introduction stage conducted by bellboys when escorting guests to their rooms.

Data 4.

Topic: Bellboy escorts guests to the room

The Interactants:

Bellboy : 18 years (M) Ayana hotel

Guest : 2 F (25 years old)

The first meeting

The context of the speech: after the check process is complete, the bellboy is ready to escort guests to his room by bringing guest luggage.

Bellboy : お部屋までご案内します。お客様のお部屋は4階です

oheya made goannai shimasu. Okyakusama no oheya wa 4 kai desu
We will escort you until the room. Your room is in floor 4.

どうぞこちらへ
Doozo kochira e
This way, please

Guest : はい
hai
Ok

Bellboy : お客様のお部屋です。どうぞ
okyakusama no oheya desu. Doozo.
This is your room. Please
お荷物はこちらにおいてもろしいですか
Onimotsu wa kochira ni oitemo yoroshii desu ka?
Can I put your luggage here?

Guest : はい。大丈夫です
hai, daijoobu desu.
Yes, never mind

Bellboy : こちらはお部屋の鍵でございます。ドアは自動ロックです。
Kochira wa oheya no kagi de gozaimasu. Doa wa jidoorokku desu.
This is your key card room. The door is automatic.
お出かけのときは必ずお持ちください。
Odekake no toki wa, kanarazu omochikudasai.
When you want to go out, remember please bring your key card room

Guest : はい
Hai
Yes

Bellboy : 非常口はローカーの突き当たりにございます。
hijooouchi wa rooka no tsukiatarini gozaimasu.
Emergency door is in the end of corridor.

Guest : はい、わかりました
hai, wakarimashita
Yes, I understand

Bellboy : ホテルの案内書はこちらです。どうぞご覧ください。
hoteru no annaisho wa kochira desu. Doozo goran kudasai.
The hotel information is here. Please see.

Guest : はい
Hai
Ok

Bellboy : ほかに御用がございませうか
hoka ni goyoo ga gozaimasu ka?
Is there anything else that you want to ask?

Guest : いいえ、えつにないです
iie, betsu ni nai desu.
No, there is no

Bellboy : お困りのときは遠慮なく内戦0番までお電話ください
okomari no toki, enryounaku naisen "0"ban made odenwa
kudasai.
If there is a problem, do not hesitate, please contact number 0

どうぞごゆっくり
 doozo goyukkuri
 Have a nice rest
 Guest : はい、ありがとう
 hai, arigatoo
 Ok, thank you

The conversation above is a conversation between the bellboy and the guest. The first meeting is on the first day guests come into the hotel. From the dialogue analysis above, overall bellboys have implemented negative politeness strategies. It can be seen from the sentence structure that uses a variety of keigo. Another hallmark of negative politeness strategies is seen in the greeting word, "okyakusama" (Mr / Mrs). The prefixes o and go are also added to objects belonging to guests or things referring to guests, such as o-heya (room), o-komari (problem), o-dekake (traveling), go-yoo (necessity).

The application of negative politeness strategies can also be identified in speech when the bellboy explains the rules for using the room to guests. "Kochira wa oheya no kagi de gozaimasu" (this is the key to the room. "doaa wa jidoorokku desu" (The key is automatic). "Odekake no toki wa, kanarazu omochikudasai" (if you want to go out, please bring the key). The addition of kanarazu (must) provide opportunities Face threats to guests Therefore bellboys use the songkeigo respect for the verb "omochi kudasai" (please bring it). Pattern "o + verb 3 + kudasai" is a subtle command sentence pattern. Other examples in dialogue 4 are "odenwa kudasai" (please call / call), "doozo goran kudasai" (please see).

At the end of the conversation, the staff showed concern with the words "okomari no toki, enryounaku naisen 0 ban made odenwakudasai" (if there are problems, don't hesitate, please call 0). This speech reflects a form of attention, the staff's concern for guests, so it can be said that the bellboy staff at the end of the conversation shows a positive politeness strategy.

From this analysis ,it can be concluded that the bellboy staff from the start of the conversation applied a negative politeness strategy. It can be identified from the use of keigo formal tutura. In the content section of the room facilities explanations, instructions are also conveyed in the formal variety of keigo as a characteristic of negative politeness strategies. Moreover, speeches that contain orders, instructions, have the opportunity to threaten guests' faces. Therefore, to protect the faces of guests, bellboys use negative politeness strategies (sub strategy 5). At the end of the conversation, the bellboy uses positive politeness strategies as an expression of care and concern for the guest and an effort to leave a positive impression on the guest's mind.

The using of Japanese at engagement Stage

At the engagement stage, the relationship between guests and staff is less rigid than at the beginning of the meeting. They have started to know each other.

Data 5. Furui Taoru

Topic: Furui Taoru (Used Towel)

The Interactants:

GRO : 47th / M (Melia Bali hotel)

Guest : 65 years (husband and wife)

The guest stays on the 3rd day

The context of the speech situation: GRO staff makes guest courtesy calls to guests. GRO staff asks about the condition of the guest room to make sure there is a problem or not. GRO approaches the guest while they are enjoying breakfast.

- GRO : おはようございます。みな様、コーヒーまだ大丈夫でしょうか
ohayoo gozaimasu mina sama. koohee mada daijoobu deshooka
Good morning sir. Is the coffee okay?
- Guest : はい、大丈夫です。
(ml) Hai, daijoobu desu.
Yes, it is okay
- GRO : 私はフロントのマデと申します、もし困ったことがございましたら、
私がフロントに下りますので起こしただければ.....お部屋のこと何か
問題ございませんでしょうか。おゆとか.....
watashi wa furonto no Made to mooshimasu, moshi komatta koto ga gozaimashi
tara watashi ga furonto ni orimasu node okoshi tadakereba...oheya no koto nani ka
mondai gozaimasen deshouka? oyu toka.....
I am Made, I am staff front office. Because I am in front desk, if there is a problem, you can
come to us. How about your room Mrs, Mr? Is there any problem? Maybe about the hot
water?
- Guest : きのう、バスケットにのこしたけど
(ml) Kinoo, basuketto ni nokoshitakedo
Yesterday, something was left in the basket
- GRO : フルーツですか
furuutsu desu ka?
Is it fruit?
- Guest : タオル
Taoru
Towel
- GRO : 交換しなかったですか
kookan shinakatta desu ka?
Has not it been replaced?
- Guest : 交換したけど
(fm) kookan shita kedo...
It has been, but
- Guest : 新しいのを交換したけど古いのが持って来れたのよ
(ml) atarashii no o kookan shita kedo.. furui no ga motte wasuretanoyo
It has been change with the new, but the older one is forget to bring
- GRO : 古いのが持って来れましたかということ
furui noga mottewasuremashita desu ka.. to iu koto de.....
Do you forget to bring the old one?
お部屋番号は?
Oheya bangoo wa?
What is your room number?
- Guest : three four two nine
- GRO : two nine. タオルですね。その他は何かお湯とかエアコン ちゃんと
つきますか
Taoru desu ne. Sono igai wa nanika oyu toka, eaakon chanto tsukimasu ka
Towel's problem...alright, any else? Such as hot water is the room air conditioner
functioning properly?
- Guest : 大丈夫
Daijoobu.
Never mind.

GRO : どうぞ楽しみください。何かございましたら私はフロントにおります
 のでおこしなされば
 doozo gotanoshimini kudasai. Nani ka gozaimashitara watashi wa furonto ni
 orimasu node. Okoshi itadakereba...
 Please have fun. If there is problem, I'm in front office, I hope you mind to come
 お願いします。失礼いたします
 Onegashimasu. Shitsurei itashimasu
 Please cooperate. Excuse me

The context of this conversation was when GRO staff did a face to face guest courtesy activity. This activity is carried out to ask for feedback, ask about problems related to service and guest comfort during their stay, so that improvements or solutions can be made. At the beginning of the conversation, GRO staff used a positive politeness strategy, as evidenced by their greeting 'good morning.' Before getting into the subject of discussion, GRO staff made small talk about the dishes served at the restaurant with the words "koohii mada daijoubu deshou ka" (how's the coffee?). It just entered the subject with the utterance "oheya no koto nani ka mondai gozaimasen deshouka? oyu toka" (regarding the room, is there a problem? Such as hot water). As Japanese communication styles generally, it is not straight to the point, but gradually. Guests answered GRO staff questions with the answer "something is left in the room basket". The staff asked again "is it fruit in the basket?" guest answered "towel". Next, the staff did not understand the meaning of the guest, so they asked again "has it not been replaced?", The guest replied "it has been replaced, but the old one is still in the basket". Japanese speaking style in a gradual / indirect manner is a common thing. This is a way to protect the face of the speech partner. Even though in this context the partner is the waiter, guests still apply the rules of courtesy of their origin country.

In data 6 above, there are a number of guest answers conveyed in short speech, such as when confirming that what was left in the room was a towel. The guest answered "taoru" (towel), without covering it with a copula desu as a sign of politeness. Likewise, when asked for the room number, the guest answered "three four two nine" without closing it desu. In the guest answer "Daijoubu" (OK / no problem) also without being closed with the copula "desu". These three guest answers were spoken without the ending desu. It shows that guests use casual (non-formal) speech. As guests who have their power are free to choose formal or informal forms. The responded by hotel staff using a positive politeness strategy. It can be seen by the use of the particle "ne" in the utterance "Taoru desu ne. Sono igai wa nanika oyu toka, eaakon chanto tsukimasu ka" (The towel problem, is there anything else? For example hot water. Is the air conditioner really functioning properly?). The guest answered "daijoubu" (no problem) in an informal utterance, without being closed with copula desu.

After making sure that the guest had no problem, GRO staff again showed concern by saying "doozo gotanoshinde kudasai" (have fun) followed by offering assistance if the guest faced any problems/complaints with the utterance "Nani ka gozaimashitara watashi wa furonto ni orimasu node ... (If there is a problem, I'm at the front office ...) Okoshi itadakereba ... (if you mind please come). In terms of the meaning and intent of the utterances, GRO staff use a positive politeness strategy, namely that there is an element of attention to hearers. On the other hand, negative politeness strategies are also used, seen in utterance (1) the variety of keigo in nouns and verbs, (2) unfinished sentence structures (hedge ~ node and ~ kereba).

As an expression of respect towards the guest, finally before saying goodbye, the staff said "Onegaishimasu. Shitsurei itashimasu" (Please cooperate. Excuse me). At the end of the conversation, GRO again shows an expression of concern for the guest. So in this section a positive politeness strategy is used. From the sentence structure, the form of kenjyogo respect is used as a characteristic of negative politeness strategies. So it can be concluded from the 5 data that GRO staff

have used positive politeness strategies, off record politeness strategies and negative politeness strategies. Negative politeness strategies can be identified from using keigo. The politeness strategy off record can be seen from small talk and sentences that are not finished with the copula "kedo". Positive politeness strategies can be seen from the speech which contains elements of paying attention to hearers.

The using of Japanese at departure Stage

Departure stage is the stage where the guest will leave the hotel. The last day of staying at the hotel. At this stage the communication between staff and guests regarding bill payment, handling of luggage and delivery to the airport. The hotel staff usually shows the gratitude to the guest for staying and looking forward to their next visit. Hotel staff used to maintain a polite attitude to leave a positive impression in the eyes of guests.

Data. 6

Topic: check out

The Interactants:

Cashier : 45 yrs / M (Ayana hotel)

Guest : 26 th / F

The context of the speech situation: a guest comes to the front desk counter, saying that she will do the checking out process.

Cashier: おはようござい

Ohayoo gozaimasu

Good morning

Guest : 1412ごしつの恵みです。チェックアウトしたいんですが

1412 goshitsu no Megumi desu. Chekku auto shitain desu ga

Megumi, room number 1412. I want to check out

Cashier: かしこまりました。部屋の鍵をお願いします

Kashikomarimashita. heya no kagi o onegaishimasu

Alright, your key room please.

Guest : はい

Hai,

Ok

Cashier: お支払いは米ドルでございますか。ルピアでございますか

oshiharai wa beidoru de gozaimasu ka, rupia de gozaimasu ka?

Do you want to use dollar or rupiah for the payment?

Guest : 米ドルでございます

Bei doru de onegaishimasu

Using dollar please

Cashier: かしこまりました。少々お待ちください。

Kashikomarimashita. Shooshoo omachi kudasai.

Ok. Wait a moment.

おまたせいたしました。

Omatase itashimashita

Sorry for making you wait.

こちらがお支払いの額となります。全部で700ドルでございます。

Kochira ga oshiharai no gaku ni narimasu. Zenbu de, 700 doru de gozaimasu.

This is the payment list. Total 700 dollars

-
- ルームナンバーとお名前を確認お願いします。
 Ruumu nambaa to onamae o kakunin onegaishimasu.
 Please re-check your room number and your name.
- Guest : はい、大丈夫です
 hai, daijoo bu desu.
 Yes, alright
- Cashier : カードをお預かりします。
 Kaado o oazukarishimasu.
 I borrow the card for a moment
 ピンをお願いします。
 pin o onegaishimasu.
 Please your pin number
 ありがとうございます。またのご利用お待ちしております。
 Arigatoo gozaimashita. Mata no goriyoo omachishite orimasu.
 Thank you. We are waiting for your coming
- Guest : ありがとうございます。じゃ、また
 Arigatoo gozaimasu. Jya, mata

Data 6 is a conversation between the cashier and guests who will do the check out process. The staff greets guests with a "good morning" greeting. This attitude is a form of positive politeness strategy, can be seen from the element of paying attention to hearers. The cashier staff has carried out the checking out process according to the procedures applied at the hotel, such as asking for room keys, checking the system for the fees incurred by guests while staying at the hotel and asking how the guests want payment method. Speech related to important points in the room check out service is conveyed with a negative politeness strategy. It can be seen from the formal keigo language, such as "heya no kagi o onegaishimasu" (please the key room), "pin o onegaishimasu" (please pin number). The verb onegaishimasu is a sign of civility in the kenjyoo variety, the staff uses respectful speech in a way that humiliates themselves. The utterance "oshiharai wa beidoru de gozaimasu ka, rupia de gozaimasu ka?" (the payment is in US dollars or rupees?), is a variety of super teineigo, and sonkeigo. Songkeigo politeness markers can be seen in the use of the word oshiharai (payment method). Addition of the prefix "o" to shiharai, is a way of exalting objects belonging to hearers. The use of the suffix "de gozaimasu" in the utterance "beidoru de gozaimasu ka, rupia de gozaimasu ka?" make this speech more subtle (super teinei). De gozaimasu is a subtle form of desu. Based on data analysis 6, it is found that the cashier staff in handling the check out process uses formal language. It can be seen from the sentence structure which is all in the form of keigo (honorific). At the beginning of the conversation, positive politeness strategies are used. The content section uses negative politeness strategies and at the end of the conversation, uses positive politeness strategies.

Positive politeness strategies at the beginning of a conversation can be identified from greetings, as an expression of concern for guests. In the content section, more negative politeness strategies are used; formal speech in the check out service procedure with the characteristic used the keigo variety. It can be seen from the sentence structure, choice of words, the three types of keigo (teineigo, sonkeigo and kenjyogo) used by cashier staff.

At the end of the conversation, the staff again used positive politeness strategies, as expressions of gratitude towards guests with the words "arigatoo gozaimasu" (thank you) and "mata no goriyoo omachishite orimasu" (we are waiting for your return). The words of goriyoo omachishite orimasu, give the impression of a hope for the arrival of guests again. So that the heart of the guest appears happy with a warm and impressive word, leaving a positive impression on the mind of the guest.

4. Conclusion

Based on the discussion above, it is concluded six points as follows. First, in hospitality services, Japanese keigo (respectful language) is used more by hotel staff. Keigo is used as an expression of staff respect towards guests / tourists. Asymmetrical relationships between staff and guests, where hotel staff act as waiters, the existence of social distancing, then use keigo. Hotel staff has always shown a friendly and polite attitude as waiters in the hospitality industry. If it is related to Brown & Levinson's theory of politeness strategies, that formal keigo speech is one of the characteristics of negative politeness strategies. However, there are also speeches that contain positive politeness strategies, off record politeness strategies. The strategy of bald on record politeness (direct speech without further ado) is not found in hospitality service communications.

Second, positive politeness strategies, it can be seen that there are some elements such as 1) speech that reflects attention to guests, for example greeting guests with greetings, 2) offering assistance, 3) promises that can benefit guests, such as when helping to handle guest complaints 4) identifiers the same, such as welcome home, so that guests feel like a big hotel family, 5) show an optimistic attitude, such as when asking guests to confirm with the characteristic use of the particle "ne". At the beginning of the pick-up at the airport, the hotel staff has shown a friendly, welcome and respectful attitude to guests. This attitude is an attempt to attract sympathy from guests, reducing the distance between speech participants. In an effort to make guests feel welcome, to be part of the extended family of hotels, to be greeted with a warm reception. Friendly attitude, attention is a form of positive politeness strategies.

Third, negative politeness strategies are shown by staff in the form of 1) choice of formal language, 2) applying distance, not wanting to disturb the guest area, giving freedom to guests, 3) speech that contains non-coercive choices, 4) starting with an apology, in imperative speech, as an effort to keep the guest's face, save the negative face of the guest.

Fourth, various futsugo (daily language) are also found in the data, especially in conversations related to handling guest complaints. So that in certain cases a short type of futsugo speech is used, in the form of a question word without a question mark (gimonshi) but spoken in an ascending tone. Repeating the guest answer with a short speech without copula desu.

Fifth, futsugo style is found at the engagement stage, where generally guests have stayed more than two days at the hotel. It can be said that guests are familiar with the hotel environment and also the hotel staff, so that futsugo speech if it is mixed with formal speech is still considered a natural thing; it does not affect guests' faces. Besides this futsugo speech appears in the dialogue when handling guest complaints. So it can be concluded that the use of futsugo is for practical communication. Short futsugo speech will be easier to catch the ear, thus facilitating communication and speeding up handling of guest complaints.

The last, the beginning of the conversation, more positive politeness strategies are applied, such as expressions of paying attention to guests, attracts guest sympathy. In the content section, you can find negative politeness strategies and positive politeness strategies depending on the context of the speech event. At the end of the conversation, return to positive politeness strategies as a form of attention and the desire to get a positive impression in the eyes of guests. So that in a dialogue can be found more than one strategy of language politeness.

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